

THEORIES OF INTERTEXTUALITY AND THE BASIC FRAMEWORK OF KRISTEVA'S FORMULATION OF HER THEORY OF INTERTEXTUALITY

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ABSTRACT

This article is explored the concept of Intertextuality primarily from a theoretical point of view. It is traced the concept of Intertextuality through its origins in Julia Kristeva to its further development in the works of Roland Barthes. The subject of Kristeva's essay in which she introduces the term "intertextuality" is the literary theory of Mikhail Mikhailovich Bakhtin, she transforms and reinterprets his literary theory and formulates her own theory of Intertextuality.

Definitions of Intertextuality. I begin by considering some definitions of the term Intertextuality. I cite Harris (1992: 175), who defines Intertextuality as follows:

1. In its broadest usage, the mode of existence of all thought, language, and discourse.
2. More narrowly, the interaction of other utterances/texts (discourses) that produces a new utterance/text (discourse).
3. A synonym for allusion.
4. In one possible interpretation of Julia Kristeva, the process that produces the text from among the manifold possibilities of the mind's contents.

Harris' definition is based on a theoretical perspective. The term Intertextuality has been widely used

outside of this definition. Graham Allen describes this use thus:

Intertextuality is one of the most commonly used and misused terms in contemporary critical vocabulary. 'An Intertextual Study of...' or 'Intertextuality and ...' are such commonplace constructions in the titles of critical works that one might be forgiven for assuming that intertextuality is a term that is generally understood and provides a stable set of critical procedures for interpretation. Nothing, in fact, could be further from the truth. The term is defined so variously that it is, currently, akin to such terms as 'The Imagination', 'history', or 'Postmodernism': terms which are... underdetermined in meaning and overdetermined in figuration (Allen, 2011: 2).

Indeed, the terms intertextuality, intertextual and intertext are often employed in contexts where they are used to represent source study, as has become common in scholarship. In order to avoid such confusion, I intend to explore the concept of intertextuality as set out in the writing of the originator of the word, Julia Kristeva, and its further development in the work of Roland Barthes.

My primary focus in this part is on the theory of Barthes. This focus is firstly motivated by the need to simplify an overwhelming, conflicting and contradicting tradition of theories related to, or called Intertextuality, and secondly, because Barthes successfully employs his theoretical framework in an analysis of a literary text, detailed in his seminal work, *S/Z*. His exposition is the one that I found the most useful to construct a conceptual framework with which to analyse the Confessions. The areas that I focus my attention on in the exploration of these theoretical approaches are: the text, or the object of literary study, the author, and the reader, and the manner in which meaning is produced through the interaction/agency of these three elements.

Once the relevant theoretical points have been identified, I proceed to explore the concepts related to Intertextuality, primarily from the perspective of Classical scholarship. The exploration of these concepts will highlight the manner in which a post-structuralist approach to Intertextuality differs from other similar methodologies often employed in Classical scholarship. These explorations will serve as the backbone for the development of a conceptual framework that will guide the interpretation of the Confessions and the

relationship it has with the Letter to the Romans.

Julia Kristeva's contribution to literary theory had its origin in another theory. The subject of Kristeva's essay in which she introduces the term "intertextuality" is the literary theory of Mikhail Mikhailovich Bakhtin. In this essay she transforms and reinterprets his literary theory and formulates her own theory of Intertextuality. She does this by fusing Saussurian linguistics with Bakhtin's literary theory. In order to understand what Kristeva contributed to literary theory, it is worth looking at the aspects of Bakhtin's theory that she uses or transforms in her own theory. Two aspects of Bakhtin's literary theory are relevant, namely, the notion of the "utterance" and his idea of "dialogism".

Dialogism and the utterance. The importance of Bakhtin's "utterance" to this study relates to Saussure's notion of the sign: in order to establish a theory of how texts convey meaning, the elements that make up texts and how they function need to be addressed. Differing significantly from the abstraction of the linguistic sign proposed by Saussure, Bakhtin understands the "utterance" as central to the meaning of any text. The utterance differs from the sign in that it possesses a social context, a human element. Whereas the sign is an abstraction, the performance of the utterance, its social significance, is what defines its meaning. The abstraction of the sign robs it of one of the key aspects which provides it with meaning.

For the purposes of the conceptual framework used in this study, the most important aspect of Bakhtin's theory developed further by Kristeva is the concept

of dialogism¹⁰. For Bakhtin, dialogism is not simply one aspect of language but a central element thereof. Bakhtin defines two kinds of texts or utterances: the monologic and the dialogic. The dialogic text is in continuous dialogue with other texts, and is informed by other texts, whereas the monologic text seeks to impose a singular logic and meaning. These terms refer to ideological perspectives. For Bakhtin, all language is dialogic, locked in the struggle between the opposing forces of the monologic and dialogic utterance. The monological text is that which imposes a singular perspective on the text, expresses a single voice; the dialogical text is a text possessing multiple voices, multiple perspectives.

Bakhtin refers to the existence of more than one simultaneous voice as polyphony, a term he borrows from music. Bakhtin describes it thus: The word is not a material thing but rather the eternally mobile, the eternally fickle medium of dialogic interaction. It never gravitates toward a single consciousness or a single voice. The life of the word is contained in its transfer from one mouth to another, from one context to another context, from one social collective to another, from one generation to another generation. In this process the word does not forget its own path and cannot completely free itself from the power of those concrete contexts into which it has entered (Bakhtin, 1984: 201).

The voice, for Bakhtin, is therefore a perspective, defined by social and literary contexts, of which there are many in any text. What Bakhtin is defining in the discussion above is a theory of how meaning is produced by texts, a central and important issue to the interpretation of any

text. The word does not possess a singular meaning, but is characterised by a number of contexts, across geographic, historical, literary and other spaces, potentially innumerable. These contexts thus inform the meaning of the word, but not in the sense of a mathematical function, whereby one would consider all these contexts (as inputs) and produce a single output, a single meaning. Rather, the word is in constant dialogue with these contexts, allowing for a multitude of meanings to emerge.

Intertextuality. In Kristeva's thought, the word "dialogism" is replaced with "intertextuality". Whereas Bakhtin uses the word "utterance" to refer to the elements of the dialogic discourse, which emphasises the social and historical context, Kristeva uses the term "word". The literary word, according to Kristeva's understanding of Bakhtin's theory, is "an intersection of textual surfaces rather than a point (a fixed meaning), as a dialogue among several writings: the writer, the addressee (or the character) and the contemporary or earlier cultural context" (Kristeva, 1986: 36).

Kristeva situates the word within a three-dimensional space within which the "various semic sets and poetic sequences function" (1986: 36). The three dimensions, "or coordinates of dialogue" of this textual space are the writing subject, the addressee and exterior texts (Kristeva, 1986: 36). The status, or meaning, of the word is defined horizontally, that is, between the writing subject and the addressee, and vertically, between the addressee and exterior texts, or an "anterior or synchronic literary corpus" (Kristeva, 1986: 36-37). Therefore, Kristeva imagines the coincidence of the horizontal and vertical axes she has described: Hence horizontal axis (subject-

addressee) and vertical axis (text-context) coincide, bringing to light an important fact: each word (text) is an intersection of word (texts) where at least one other word (text) can be read... any text is constructed as a mosaic of quotations; any text is the absorption and transformation of another. The notion of intertextuality replaces that of intersubjectivity, and poetic language is read as at least double. (Kristeva, 1980: 66).

In distinction to Bakhtin, Kristeva considers the word not as an intersection of voices, but rather an intersection of texts. Kristeva, in "Le mot, le dialogue et le roman", also criticises Saussure's concept of the sign. The sign, according to Saussure, is, as Kristeva puts it, "a product of scientific abstraction", "a vertically and hierarchically linear division", while poetic language is double in the sense of "one and other" (Kristeva, 1980: 69). The term sign, as understood by Saussure, cannot be applied to poetic language. Poetic language is subject to "an infinity of pairings and combinations" (Kristeva, 1980: 69). In a similar vein, Allen (2011: 44-45) describes Intertextuality as a kind of language which resists a singular, absolute logic; meaning is not finite, it is subverted or resisted. To clarify here, poetic language, according to Kristeva, is always multivalent: there will always be traces of other texts (and, for example, other contexts, voices or narrators) in poetic language. For Kristeva, abstraction such as attempted by Saussurian linguistics, to reduce the text to a collection of signs, is not possible, because of the infinite possibilities that poetic language produces.

Significance. The discussion above describes the basic framework of Kristeva's formulation of her theory of Intertextuality.

Rather appropriately, the term "intertextuality" was quickly appropriated by other scholars, as remarked above, and was slowly transformed to refer to influence, allusion or simple source study, a fact she laments in "La révolution du langage poétique" (1984, 59-60). In response to this, Kristeva reformulated her theory in different terms. In "La révolution du langage poétique" she develops her theory beyond the earlier essays. At this stage, her theory is heavily influenced by the terminology of psychoanalysis, particularly that of Jacques Lacan. She is interested in refining the signifying process, which she calls signification. She defines this as "precisely this unlimited and unbounded generating process, this unceasing operation of the drives toward, in, and through language; toward, in, and through the exchange system and its protagonists – the subject and his institutions" (Kristeva, 1984:17). She describes the process as the sum of two inseparable "modalities", namely the semiotic and the symbolic (Kristeva, 1984: 24). For Kristeva, the symbolic represents the rational, the logical, the part which can be understood completely. It represents the point at which the subject enters into society and is subject to social structures, including linguistic structures (Kristeva, 1984: 29). The semiotic, on the other hand, is the irrational, the illogical, the desires and drives of the subject. She explains that every signifying system relies on a dialectic between the semiotic and the symbolic. From this dialectic, Kristeva develops a theory of how texts function. She identifies two aspects of the text which she labels the "genotext" and the "phenotext". The genotext is pervaded by the semiotic, which she defines as "the

only transfer of drive energies that organizes a space in which the subject is not yet a split unity that will become blurred, giving rise to the symbolic” (Kristeva, 1984: 86). The genotext is not linguistic, in the sense of being able to be reduced to grammatical or linguistic parts or structures, but rather what Kristeva considers a process, that is, continually working (Kristeva, 1984: 86). Out of the genotext, the phenotext emerges. The phenotext is the text that tries to communicate, which is seated in the symbolic, and therefore logical. Unlike the genotext, the phenotext can be reduced to its constituent parts and is structured. The phenotext represents what can be understood and the genotext that which resists comprehension, which undermines it. The genotext is the primary characteristic of what Kristeva terms “poetic language”. In an attempt to explain how poetic language is understood, Kristeva revisits her earlier theory of Intertextuality. She identifies a process in the unconscious, the “passage from one sign system to another” (Kristeva, 1984: 59):

The new signifying system may be produced with the same signifying material; in language, for example, the passage may be made from narrative to text. Or it may be borrowed from different signifying materials: the transposition from a carnival scene to the written text, for instance... The term inter-textuality denotes this transposition of one (or several) sign system(s) into another; but since this term has often been understood in the banal sense of ‘study of sources,’ we prefer the term transposition because it specifies that the passage from one signifying system to another demands a new articulation of the

thetic – of enunciative and denotative positionality. If one grants that every signifying practice is a field of transpositions of various signifying systems (an inter-textuality), one then understands that its ‘place’ of enunciation and its denoted ‘object’ are never single, complete, and identical to themselves, but always plural, shattered, capable of being tabulated. In this way polysemy can also be seen as the result of a semiotic polyvalence (Kristeva, 1984: 59-60).

Several things can be gleaned from this challenging passage. Kristeva highlights the possibility that different kinds of signifying materials may operate in the same signifying system. Literature is not only characterised by linguistic material in the composition of its signifying system(s), but characterised by other materials too that are capable of signifying. A text is not merely a collection of (linguistic) texts, but a fabric of different signifying materials. Because the text is woven from these different, linguistic and non-linguistic “threads”, they pull against stable meaning and generate polysemy. The phenotext, that part which can be understood, is undermined by the efforts of the genotext to unleash these different signifying materials.

The Addressee. Kristeva presents an articulation of what a text is and how the signification process functions, but the position of the author and reader is not concretely defined in her theory. She does describe the position of the “addressee” in her theory: “The addressee, however, is included within a book’s discursive universe only as discourse itself. He thus fuses with this other discourse, this other book, in relation to which the writer has written his own text” (Kristeva, 1980: 66).

The author is transformed into the “writing subject”. The writing subject refers also to the conscious and the unconscious of the writer, but both of these remain inaccessible. Leon S. Roudiez, in the introduction to the translation of *La révolution du langage poétique*, warns against trying to psychoanalyse the writer through his text, and through it somehow explain the text (Kristeva, 1984:8). In Kristeva’s theory, the text is the primary point of departure.

Criticism of Kristeva’s theory. The description of Kristeva’s theory above does serve to highlight the complexity of Kristeva’s writing. Her love of mathematical language has made her work very difficult to interpret. This fact has also made her subject to significant criticism from scholars from the fields of Mathematics and Science. A chapter is devoted to her literary theory in Sokal and Bricmont’s work *Fashionable Nonsense: Postmodern Intellectuals’ Abuse of Science* (1998: 38-49). They note the errors in her use of mathematical language in the theory, particularly her understanding of set theory, Boolean logic, and her own concept of “poetic logic”¹⁸. While Kristeva does insist that her use of

notions of set theory and other mathematical language is metaphorical, Sokal and Bricmont do not see any justification for the use of such language, metaphorical or otherwise (1998: 42). The mathematical language, combined with the metaphorical use, makes it significantly challenging to understand the precise sense that Kristeva is trying to convey regarding the mechanics of her theory. It is therefore challenging to distil a unifying “system” from the theoretical texts discussed above. Accepting the criticism of Sokal and Bricmont, I attempt to restate the elements of Kristeva’s theory crucial for the formulation of a conceptual framework in a more systematic way here. These elements, taken together with the elements from Barthes’ theory, will form the backbone of the conceptual framework that will be employed for the analysis of the *Confessions*.

Summary of Kristeva’s theory. In order to contain the scope of the theory addressed in this article, I highlight the primary aspects of Kristeva’s theory that I employ in my development of a conceptual framework for the analysis of the *Confessions*.

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